

Interfacial Bond of UHPC Reinforced with Shape Memory Alloy Bars

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Abstract:

The bond strength between precast ultra high performance concrete (UHPC) and cast-in-place UHPC is a critical factor influencing the practical application of precast UHPC systems; however, its bond behavior remains insufficiently clarified. This study focuses on the bond behavior of precast and cast-in-place UHPC interface reinforced with Shape Memory Alloy (SMA) bars under a three-point bending experiment. A strain-based method for measuring bond separation is developed and validated against experimental results to evaluate the effectiveness of SMA bars relative to steel reinforcement in enhancing bond separation strength. The effect of surface roughness in terms of smooth and grooved surfaces is also investigated. The SMA bars improved the bond strength by up to 190% compared to steel bars, despite having only about half the axial rigidity of the steel reinforcement. The fiber bridging mechanism of steel fibers is found to play an important role in grooved interfaces.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) is an innovative material with superior compressive and tensile strength compared to conventional concrete. The discrete steel fibers in UHPC effectively mitigate the inherent brittleness and help maintain the load-bearing capacity even after cracking, owing to their strain-hardening behavior. The fiber bridging effect of steel fibers in the UHPC matrix enhances resistance to crack propagation (Zerfu et al., 2025). Additionally, its dense matrix and high cohesiveness contribute to remarkable bond strength and long-term durability (Zhao and Luo, 2024; Wei et al., 2023). These characteristics make it possible to reduce structural weight and have promoted its growing adoption in the precast industry, particularly in bridge construction. However, due to transportation limitations, prefabricated UHPC segments are generally produced in lengths shorter than 20 meters, which necessitates the formation of joints between segments. To ensure proper integration between precast UHPC segments, a reliable interfacial bond between the precast segments and cast-in-place UHPC must be established as a fundamental requirement. Shape memory alloy (SMA) bars have shown promising results in crack mitigation in reinforced concrete (Chen and Andrawes, 2025). Thus, SMA bars could help close cracks at cold joints, thereby promoting long-term structural integration, and can be activated simply by heating rather than labor-intensive mechanical tensioning. However, the interfacial bond stress between precast and cast-in-place UHPC remains unclear, and to the author’s best knowledge, no studies have investigated the interface behavior between precast and cast-in-place UHPC reinforced with SMA bars. To address this research gap, the present study investigates the bond strength behavior between precast and cast-in-place UHPC reinforced with SMA bars. Three-point bending tests are conducted on precast and cast-in-place UHPC segments. The effects of SMA bars and surface roughness are evaluated. A strain-based measurement of bond separation strength is developed to compare the effectiveness of SMA bars with that of steel reinforcement.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Table 1 presents the mix composition of the UHPC used in this study, which achieved a 28-day compressive strength of 135 MPa. For this study, smooth Ni-Ti-Nb SMA wires with a diameter of 6.4 mm were employed, and the SMA bar exhibited a post-activation elastic modulus of 50.84 GPa and a yield strength of 498 MPa, determined using the 0.2 % offset method, and developed a recovery stress of 280 MPa (Andrawes et al., 2026). These values were derived from the research conducted by Andrawes et al. (2026), and detailed descriptions of the methodology can be found therein.

Table 1. Mix proportions of UHPC

Water-to-binder-ratio, W/B (%)	Water	Cement	Silica fume	Silica sand	Silica powder	Water reducing agent (%)	Volume fraction (%)	
							Steel fiber	Polypropylene fiber
19.7	0.225	1.00	0.25	1.10	0.30	4.47	1.00	0.50

The objective of this study is to examine the influence of SMA bars on the interfacial bond behavior between precast UHPC substrates and cast-in-place UHPC. The presence of SMA bars enhances joint stress through the prestressing effect induced by heat activation after installation at the joint. The effect of surface condition, including smooth or grooved surfaces, is also studied. For this purpose, flexural specimens were fabricated in accordance with ASTM C1609 (ASTM, 2007). A total of 5 specimens were prepared, each with dimensions of 100 mm × 100 mm × 400 mm (Table 2). The specimens were cast in flexural molds containing a 6 mm diameter hole with a side cover thickness of 20 mm to accommodate the reinforcing bars. For comparison with the SMA-reinforced specimens, a No. 2 deformed steel bar was used as the

reference reinforcement. The precast concrete was initially cast into specimens measuring 100 mm × 100 mm × 200 mm. Wooden blocks were used to prepare grooved and smooth UHPC surfaces, and crimps were used in the SMA bars to improve bond performance.

Table 2. Details of test variables.

Specimens	Surface condition	Bar type	Number of bars
USN	Smooth	No Bar	N/A
USS	Smooth	Steel bar	1
UGS	Grooved	Steel bar	
USP2	Smooth	SMA bar	2
UGP2	Grooved	SMA bar	

The test setup is shown in Figure 1. Two strain gauges were attached at a distance of 25 mm from the top and the bottom.

Figure 1. Detailed test setup for three-point loading

3. TEST RESULTS

In this study, bond strength is defined as the force required to completely separate the precast and cast-in-place concrete surfaces. As shown in Figure 2, the top strain first goes into compression as the loading increases. However, when the complete separation occurs between the two surfaces, the top strain becomes zero and then increases in tension. When there is no reinforcement in the specimen, the load reaches its peak load and suddenly drops when the top strain becomes zero. This peak load is defined as the bond strength in this study. The top strain and load-deflection response of the specimen with precast and cast-in-place UHPC with a smooth interface and no reinforcement (USN) is shown in Figure 2(b) to validate this method. For the specimens with reinforcement going through the interface, the reinforcement keeps resisting the load after the bond separation, and the entire load is taken by the reinforcement. As this study is focused on the bond strength of the two concrete interfaces, the peak load is not considered in this study. The load required for complete bond separation is obtained from the top strain vs load response curves for all specimens. The strain vs load responses of the specimens are shown in Figure 3. As there is no prestress applied to the steel rebar reinforced specimens, the curves start with zero initial top strain. The SMA bars were activated with electricity and reached a temperature of 200⁰ C. After activation and cooling of the SMA, the stable strains were recorded and reported as the initial strain in Figure 3. For the specimen with two SMA bars and a smooth UHPC surface (USP2), the eccentricity of the SMA bars due to the placement of 25mm below the center leads to a tensile strain of 1092 micro strain on the top. However, the specimen

with two SMA bars and a grooved surface (UGP2) exhibits a top strain of 108 microstrains in compression. This indicates that the full section goes into compression upon activation of the SMA bar.

Figure 2. Definition of bond strength (a) complete interface separation at zero top strain (b) capacity reduction after top strain reaches zero strain for a specimen without any reinforcement

Figure 3. Load vs top strain response of specimens. (a) USS (b) UGS (c) USP2 (d) UGP2
The interfacial strength can be used to indicate the degree of bond resistance between the precast and cast-in-place concrete. For evaluating the interfacial strength of the joint under three-point loading, the interfacial strength (σ) is calculated using Eq. (1).

$$\sigma = \frac{3PL}{2bh^2} \quad (1)$$

Where P is the applied load, L represents the span length between the supports, and b and h correspond to the cross-sectional width and height, respectively. To assess the effectiveness of SMA bars, two SMA bars with a cross-sectional diameter of 6 mm are used for the SMA reinforced specimens, whereas one steel bar is used for the steel reinforced specimens. It should be noted that the post-activation stiffness of SMA bars is significantly lower than that of the steel rebars. The post-activation stiffness of SMA bars is 50.84 GPa, whereas the stiffness or modulus of elasticity of steel bars is 200 GPa. Thus, the modulus of elasticity of steel bars is 4 times higher than that of the SMA bars. Even with two SMA bars, the axial rigidity of steel bars (EA) is approximately 2 times higher than that of the SMA bars. Thus, it can be concluded that at least

four SMA bars are required to obtain a fair comparison with the steel bars in terms of axial rigidity. The shape memory effect (SME) of SMA bars plays an important role in significantly increasing the bond strength of the specimens by compressing the interface (Figure 4). The specimens with SMA bars show significant improvements in bond strength compared to the specimens with steel bars with both smooth and grooved surfaces. When SMA bars are used, the bond strength increased by 183% and 190% for the smooth interface and grooved interface, respectively, compared to the specimens with one steel bar. Grooved interfaces showed higher bond strength across all specimens. The bond strength of the specimen with a grooved surface and steel reinforcement (UGS) increases by 7.0% compared to the specimens with a smooth surface and steel reinforcement (USS). When SMA bars are used, the specimen with a grooved surface (UGP2) showed 9.4% improvement in bond strength compared to the specimen with a smooth surface (USP2). Bond separation is delayed in the grooved specimen due to the fiber bridging effect of UHPC. As the failure mode is a typical tensile mode of crack separation (mode I), the grooves start breaking as the crack propagates. The steel fibers within the grooves increase the cracking load and stiffness through the fiber-bridging mechanism. This phenomenon can be observed by comparing specimens with a smooth surface and a grooved surface, as shown in Figure 4(b).

Figure 4. (a) Interface bond strength of the specimens and (b) The effect of surface types (i) Smooth surface (ii) Grooved surface

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the interfacial bond strength between precast and cast-in-place ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) reinforced with shape memory alloy (SMA) bars. To this end, joint strength was evaluated by applying three-point loading to concrete prisms. A strain-based method was proposed and validated to obtain the bond separation strength. The complete bond separation was defined as the top strain changes from compression to tension. The key findings of this study are as follows:

- (1) Active prestressing with SMA bars significantly increased the bond strength of precast and cast-in-place UHPC compared to passive steel reinforcement. The specimens with two SMA bars exhibited 183% and 190% improvement in bond strength for the smooth and the grooved surfaces, respectively, compared to the specimens with steel bars. Thus, the SMA bars were found to be effective and improved the bond strength up to 190% with an axial rigidity (EA) half that of the steel bars.
- (2) The specimens with grooved surfaces showed improved performance in all cases. The grooved surface increased the bond strength by 7% and 9.4% for specimens reinforced with steel and SMA, respectively.

This study focused on evaluating the effectiveness of SMA bars in enhancing the bond strength of precast and cast-in-place UHPC interfaces. The results suggest that SMA bars may be used as supplementary reinforcement to mitigate crack opening and bond separation at critical interfaces in concrete infrastructure cast with UHPC.

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